

Polarographic Study of Complex Formed by Lead with 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane Tetra-acetic Acid

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Reduction of lead in 1,2-diaminocyclohexane tetra-acetic acid has been studied at an ionic strength of 0.1 at different pHs, using dropping mercury electrode. At pH 1, only one wave appears, which corresponds to the reduction of Pb^{2+} in noncomplexing media. At higher pH (1.68), two waves appear, the first wave corresponding to the reduction of Pb^{2+} in noncomplexing media; the second wave is due to the reduction of lead-CDTA complex. Beyond pH 1.68, more and more of lead is complexed with CDTA. The complex is stable above pH 5.0. The reduction of lead-CDTA complex is an irreversible process. The results of the amperometric titrations of $Pb(II)$ -CDTA at different pHs suggest the formation of 1:1 complex (above pH 5). The stability constant of the complex has been calculated by the displacement method. The value of $\log K_{st}$ comes to be 19.60 at 30° ($\mu = 0.1$). Effect of temperature and ionic strength on the stability constant has been studied. A method has been suggested for determination of Tl^+ and Pb^{2+} in presence of each other.

1,2-Diaminocyclohexane tetra-acetic acid (CDTA) forms stable complex with a number of metal ions; the stability constants of the chelates formed by this compound are higher in comparison to those formed by ethylenediamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA)¹. Yoshino² and Ishibashi³ have used EDTA as the supporting electrolyte during analysis of lead. Schwarzenbach and co-workers⁴ have calculated the stability constants of the CDTA complexes with many metal ions by pH and potentiometric measurements. Selmer⁵ has calculated the stability constant of $Bi(III)$ -CDTA complexes by the displacement method, previously applied by Schwarzenbach. Sundaram and co-workers⁶ have studied the $Fe(II)$ -CDTA complexes by polarographic and spectrophotometric methods. Cu^{2+} has been reported to reduce reversibly in solutions of CDTA⁶⁻⁷. Recently Moeller and co-workers⁸⁻⁹ have studied the interaction of CDTA and the tripositive rare earth metal ions, employing mercury-indicator technique and titration method. We have already studied the complexes of lanthanum (III), europium (III), and ytterbium (III) polarographically and the stability constants have been calculated¹⁰. The present communication describes the polarographic study of the complex formation by $Pb(II)$ with the anion of CDTA.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. R. grade lead nitrate was dissolved in conductivity water and the solution was standardised by titrating against potassium chromate by an amperometric end point.

1. Schwarzenbach, *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, **37**, 937.
2. *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1957, **78**, 131.
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5. *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, **32**, 450.
6. Pecsok, *Anal. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 281.
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8. Moeller and Thompson *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 499.
9. Moeller and Hsueh, *ibid.*, 1962, **24**, 1635.
10. Jain and Gaur, Paper presented at the IIIrd International Congress of Polarography, 19-25th July, 1964, Southampton (U.K.).

CDTA supplied by L. Light & Co. was used as such without further purification. Solution of its disodium salt (Na_2Z) was prepared and stored in polyethylene bottles. In the amperometric study, different buffers were used for the $p\text{H}$ control. Thus $p\text{H}$ 2 and 3 were controlled by Sorensen's citrate buffer and $p\text{H}$ 8 by Sorensen's phosphate buffer. For $p\text{H}$ 7 and 10, ammonium acetate and ammonium chloride-ammonium hydroxide buffer were used respectively. Perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide were used for $p\text{H}$ adjustment in polarography. Ionic strength was kept constant by addition of sodium perchlorate (0.1M) or potassium nitrate. Triton X_{100} was employed as maximum suppressor. Solution of Cu^{2+} was prepared by dissolving A.R. copper nitrate and standardised as usual.

Heyrovsky system L. P. 55 D. C. polarograph was used manually. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m=2.12$ mg./sec, $t=3.6$ sec. (at an applied potential of -1.0V vs. S. C. E. in 0.1M potassium nitrate). Conventional H-type cell was employed during polarographic study. Purified hydrogen was used for removal of dissolved oxygen. All the measurements were carried out at $30^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ unless otherwise stated. Haake type 4 ultra thermostat was employed for this purpose. The $p\text{H}$ of the solution was measured by a battery-operated bench type Cambridge $p\text{H}$ meter. For amperometric titrations, a saturated potassium nitrate-agar agar bridge was employed. The diffusion current obtained after each addition of the titrant was corrected for the small dilution effect by multiplying the observed value by a factor $(V+v)/V$, where v is the volume of the titrant added up to the given stage, and V is the original volume of the solution to be titrated.

Since the reduction of the lead-CDTA complex is an irreversible process, the stability constant could not be calculated by measuring the shift in the half-wave potential¹¹.

The method, as applied by Schwarzenbach and co-workers¹² for EDTA complexes involving determination of free Cu^{2+} in presence of its complex polarographically, was employed. Potassium nitrate was used to maintain constant ionic strength which at the same time acted as a supporting electrolyte; sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer was used to control the $p\text{H}$ of the solution. The solution containing Cu^{2+} and Cu-CDTA complex was found to produce two well-defined reduction waves at the d.m.e. The first wave appeared at about $+0.08$ V vs. S.C.E. which corresponded to the reduction of Cu^{2+} to the metallic state. The second wave having an $E_{1/2}$ about 0.42 V vs. S. C. E. corresponded to the reduction of the Cu-CDTA complex. The two waves were well separated and the i_d (diffusion current) value remained constant between these two waves.

Mixtures containing copper-CDTA complex (0.001M), $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (0.001M), sodium acetate (0.01M), acetic acid (0.01M) were prepared and potassium nitrate was added to keep a constant ionic strength (0.1). Triton X_{100} (0.001%) was added to suppress the maxima and solutions were made to a fixed mark. Solutions were also prepared for 1.0 ionic strength. All the solutions were placed in the thermostat for 48 hr. and were well shaken to ensure complete reaction and then polarographed after deaeration. The i_d value of free Pb^{2+} was evaluated from the polarograms at $E = -0.2$ V vs. S. C. E. Amount of free copper in the above solution was calculated by taking a blank polarogram of Cu^{2+} in potassium nitrate.

11. Kolthoff and Lingane, "Polarography", Interscience Publication, Vol. I, 2nd ed., 1952, p. 214
12. Schwarzenbach *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4196.

The equilibrium constant (K) of the reaction

was calculated from the percentage of uncomplexed copper in mixtures as given by

$$K = \frac{[\text{Cu}^{2+}]^2}{[100 - \% \text{Cu}^{2+}]^2} \quad \dots \text{(I)}$$

The value of K_{MZ} was calculated by

$$K = \frac{K_{\text{MZ}}}{K_{\text{CuZ}}} \quad \dots \text{(II)}$$

where K_{MZ} and K_{CuZ} denote the stability constants of Pb-CDTA complex and Cu-CDTA complex, respectively. The value of K_{MZ} is given by

$$K_{\text{MZ}} = K \cdot K_{\text{CuZ}} \quad \dots \text{(III)}$$

The value of K_{CuZ} as reported by Schwarzenbach is $10^{21.3}$; therefore the value of K_{MZ} could be calculated, knowing the value of K .

Polarographic Study

At pH 1.0, a single reduction wave appeared. The half-wave potential of the wave was -0.385 V vs. S.C.E., which was the same as for the reduction of Pb^{2+} in noncomplexing media. At pH 1.68, two waves, however, appeared. The height of the first wave was considerably smaller than that of the second wave. The half-wave potential of the first wave remained at -0.38 V, but that of the second wave was found to be -0.762 V. At higher pH , the height of the second wave decreased and above pH 2.34, the first wave completely vanished; only a single wave appeared, half-wave potential of which shifted towards the more negative side as the pH increased. Above pH 4.26 and 5.04, the reduction wave combined with the wave due to hydrogen discharge. At pH 7.0 and higher, no reduction wave appeared before the decomposition of the supporting electrolyte. The polarograms at different pH s are shown in Fig. 1(A) and Fig 1(B). The results have been recorded in Table I.

FIG. 1A. Polarograms of Pb^{2+} in CDTA at different pH .
Curve a: $pH=1.0$; b: $pH=1.65$; c: $pH=2.0$; d: $pH=2.32$; e: $pH=2.56$; f: $pH=3.20$.
Each curve begins at $-0.2V$ and each interval along the axis corresponds to $-0.1V$.

FIG. 1B
Polarograms of Pb^{2+} in CDTA.
(g) $pH=4.26$. (h) $pH=5.04$.

The temperature coefficient of diffusion current of lead-CDTA complex was found to be of the order of 1.1%. The plot of $\log i/(i_d - i)$ vs. $E_{d,e}$ for the reduction wave of the complex

was found to be linear, but the value of the slope was found to be much higher than that required for the two-electron reversible reduction of the complex. Effect of the ligand concentration on the diffusion current at a constant pH (2.32) has been studied and the results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE I

$Pb^{2+} = 1.0mM$. $Na_2Z = 2.0 mM$. Ionic strength = 0.1.

pH of soln.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs. S.C.E.).	i_d .	Temp. coeff. of i_d (%) for Pb-CDTA.	Slope.
1.00	0.385	7.250 μA	..	0.032 V
1.68	Ist wave 0.380 IIInd 0.762	1.450 5.870	.. 1.20	0.033 0.110
2.00	Ist 0.385 IIInd 0.822	0.528 6.950	.. 1.20	.. 0.112
2.32	Ist 0.865	7.120	1.12	0.140
2.56	IIInd 0.870	7.260	1.10	1.140
3.20	1.052	6.070	..	..
4.26	1.390	..	..	..
5.04	1.580	..	..	..
7.00	..	..	..	..
10.00	..	..	..	..

TABLE II

pH of the soln. = 2.32.

Concentration of Pb^{2+} .	Concentration of Na_2Z .	$Pb^{2+} : Na_2Z$.	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (-V vs. S.C.E.).	i_d .
1.0 mM	1.0 mM	1:1	0.843	6.956 μA
1.0	2.0	1:2	0.862	6.864
1.0	3.0	1:3	0.902	6.798
1.0	4.0	1:4	0.915	6.798

The half-wave potential shifted towards the more negative side with the increasing concentration of the ligand, indicating that the second reduction wave was due to the reduction of the lead-CDTA complex.

Composition of the Complex

Amperometric Titrations.—Amperometric titrations of solutions containing the same amount of Pb^{2+} (at different pH) with CDTA were carried out. Results of direct titrations are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

$Pb(NO_3)_2$ soln. taken = 20 ml.

No.	pH of soln.	Conc. ratio.	Na_2Z soln. reqd.	Ratio at equiv. point.	Complex formed.	Applied voltage (V vs. S.C.E.)
1	2.0	0.001M- $Pb(NO_3)_2$ +0.01M- Na_2Z	1.67 ml	1:0.835		-0.45
2	3.0	Do	1.75	1:0.875		-0.50
3	4.0	Do	1.70	1:0.850		-0.50
4	5.0	Do	2.01	1:1.005	PbZ^{2-}	-0.48
5	7.0	Do	1.98	1:0.990	PbZ^{2-}	-0.50
6	8.0	Do	2.00	1:1.00	PbZ^{2-}	-0.51

Between pH 2 and 4, the value of Pb^{2+}/Na_2Z appeared to be less than 1. At higher pHs (5-8) the ratio of $Pb^{2+} : Na_2Z$ was, however, found to be 1:1. Direct titration at pH 10 could not be carried out due to hydrolysis of the lead salt. Reverse titrations were also carried out at a pH range of 7-10. In this range the value of Pb^{2+}/Na_2Z was also found to be 1 (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Reverse titration of lead with CDTA amperometrically.
 Na_2Z soln = 5.0 ml.

pH of the soln.	Concentration ratio.	Pb(NO ₃) ₂ soln.	Ratio at equiv point.	Complex formed.	Applied voltage (V vs. S.C.E.)
7.00	0.025M Pb ²⁺ 0.01M Na ₂ Z	2.02 ml	1.01:1.0	PbZ ²⁻	-0.50
8.00	Do	2.00	1.01:1.0	PbZ ²⁻	-0.52
10.00	Do	1.95	0.975:1.0	PbZ ²⁻	-0.52

Stability Constant

Stability constant of the complex was calculated by the method already described. Effect of temperature and ionic strength on stability constant have been studied and the results are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Temp.	μ .	Uncomplexed Cu ²⁺ .	Log K_{Mz} .	$K_{Mz} \times 10^{19}$.
30°	0.1	12.50%	19.60	4.06
30°	1.0	7.85	19.16	1.45
40°	0.1	9.28	19.32	2.09

DISCUSSION

The above results show that at pH 1.0 no complex formation occurs between Pb²⁺ and anion of the CDTA. As the pH increases, formation of complex takes place, but whole of the Pb²⁺ is not complexed, which is shown by the polarograms at pH 1.68 and 2.0. As the pH increases, more and more of lead is complexed and above pH 2.34, whole of the lead is complexed with CDTA, producing a single reduction wave. The composition of the complex, as determined by amperometric titrations, shows that 1:1 complex is formed between Pb²⁺ and anion of CDTA. The complex is stable above pH 5. The reduction of the complex is diffusion-controlled but not reversible and hence the stability constant could not be calculated by the classical method. A method devised by Schwarzenbach *et al.*¹² has been used to find out the stability constant. The value of log K_{Mz} at 30° ($\mu=0.1$) is found to be 19.60 which is in agreement with the value reported by Schwarzenbach by potentiometric titration. The slightly low value in our case may be due to the difference in temperature (the value reported by Schwarzenbach is at 20°). The effect of ionic strength on stability constant showed a decrease in the stability of the complex with the increase of ionic strength. With increase of temperature, the stability constant decreases, showing that complex is less stable at higher temperatures.

Since Tl⁺ does not form complex with CDTA in the acidic medium, Pd²⁺ can be determined in presence of Tl⁺ amperometrically at an applied voltage of -0.38 V vs. S. C. E.

at the pH range of 5 to 7. At this applied voltage Tl^+ will not be reduced and the decrease in the diffusion current will be due to complex formation between Pb^{2+} and anion of CDTA.

Similarly Tl^+ can be determined in presence of Pb^{2+} amperometrically at an applied voltage of -0.46 V vs. S. C. E. by titrating against a standard potassium chromate solution. A solution of disodium salt of CDTA (pH 6-7) is used to mask the reaction of Pb^{2+} . The same can also be carried out polarographically since at pH 5 and above, lead forms non-reducible complex with CDTA, whereas thallium does not.

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